

Collaboration practices between people and tools: the case of “*Snorra Edda. A collaborative bibliography (SnECB)*”

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The project *Snorra Edda. A collaborative bibliography (SnECB)*, <https://dh.dlms.univr.it/bib-arc/snecb/index.html> is an online bibliographical resource revolving around the topic Snorri Sturluson's *Edda* (*SnE*, 1220 ca.).¹ This is a medieval Icelandic handbook for poets-to-be and qualifies as one of the main sources for the knowledge of Old Norse mythology. The huge list of publications touching upon *SnE* is evidence of the great popularity and reception that the work has enjoyed in scholarship across epochs and cultures. However, the publication of the related bibliographical corpus is a complex task, not just because of the great amount of primary and secondary sources starting from its *edition principes* (1665), but also due to the great degree of variability within text tradition and editorial scholarship as well.

In order to create our bibliographical database, we have first examined relevant Snorrian repertoires, the main bibliographies on old Icelandic literature and on Nordic mythology among the others. For the latest updates, we have consulted several online resources and collections in search for new contributions to the topic (cfr. *c*) *The database: SnECB* at <https://dh.dlms.univr.it/bib-arc/snecb/snorribib.html>). Concerning bibliographical resources within the field of DH, we considered projects such as the Skaldic Project (<https://skaldic.org/m.php?p=skpbibliography>) or the *Bibliography of the International Arthurian Society* (<https://bias.internationalarthuriansociety.com/>) among the others.

Our new collaborative database has been created by following a good degree of FAIRness and it represents an opportunity of scholarly collaboration between people and between tools. First, anyone willing to contribute in populating the library is free to join a Zotero public group library called *snorraedda* (<https://www.zotero.org/groups/1314983/snorraedda>) that to date counts 3709 bibliographical entries. Data and related metadata can be added in the library by following the guidelines provided by Zotero and the *SnECB* rationale. Each entry displays its own metadata, but it is also enriched with specific tags and it is related to other parent or child items.

The data stored in the Zotero library can be exported in a customized XML/TEI format. However, although Zotero does pro-

vide an exporting functionality, this does not include related items, that's the reason why we implemented a Python script that assembles the exported XML/TEI files by directly accessing the Zotero API. The exported data and metadata serve for visualization and search through a customized front-end application built on top of TEI Publisher (<https://teipublisher.com/>).

The application displays the data following the Zotero model (in a simplified version), and enables users to retrieve and browse the available content by means of filters corresponding to specific metadata (e.g., subcollections, authors, dates, tags) or simply by entering a string of characters. For example, say you want to search all the publications by the author 'Maria Adele Cipolla' and you want to sort them by date: from the main page 'open' the database and once you are inside it, on the top bar choose 'sort by' -> 'date', 'filter by' -> 'author', 'filter' -> + type 'Cipolla'. As a result, you will get all the items published by this author ordered e.g. from the oldest to the latest (see Figure 1). You can further refine the search by selecting other parameters, such as 'subcollections' (that is item typologies) or 'tags'. Beyond visualizing and searching the database, users can also 'download' each entry in different formats (TEI, TeX, ePUB) directly from the Web application (Figure 2), or go back to the collaborative Zotero library through the link provided.

By selecting 'view more' you can access all data and metadata associated to a single entry, including related items (Figure 3).

Figure 1: Screenshot of the TEI publisher dashboard for browsing and searching the snorraedda

Figure 2: Screenshot of generated XML/TEI file of a single entry that can be downloaded from the UI

Figure 3: Screenshot of the customised TEI Publisher UI for visualising a bibliographic entry

The code of the customized TEI application of the project and of the Python script for exporting content to TEI from the Zotero API are publicly released on GitHub (<https://github.com/dlls-piattaforme/teipublisher-snecb>, <https://github.com/dlls-piattaforme/zotero-to-teipublisher>) to favour the exploitation of the approach in other projects. In conclusion, we believe this kind of tool collaboration (Zotero+TEI Publisher), enabled by the Python script that we implemented, could be a viable and effective solution in many situations aiming to develop a customizable web app for browsing and searching bibliographic data collaboratively collected.

Notes

1. We would like to thank our IT staff, especially Fabrizio Chiarlo and Mattia Carli (both University of Verona) for all the technical work they have done on this project.

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